

APPLYING THE ENTREPRENEURIAL EXPERIENCE OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES IN THE UNITED STATES TO THE CONTEXT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article explores the entrepreneurial success of U.S. educational services and their applicability to Uzbekistan. It highlights how the U.S. blends government oversight with private sector innovation, fostering quality and growth, particularly in EdTech and private higher education, which outpaces public institutions two to one. Key success drivers—technology, venture capital, and startups—are contrasted with challenges like inequality and high costs. The article examines potential barriers and opportunities for adapting these lessons in Uzbekistan, emphasizing the need for innovation and private sector engagement to enhance education.*

Keywords: *U.S. education system, private education sector, EdTech startups, promoting innovation, venture capital investments, online education platforms, education services market, technology adoption, improving education quality, balance between private and public sectors.*

Introduction. In the U.S., it is widely believed that a mixed approach to education, balancing government oversight and private entrepreneurship, is essential for fostering innovation and delivering high-quality educational services. This approach requires the collaborative efforts of sectors such as public schools, private schools, and nonprofit educational organizations. Adapting such experiences to the context of Uzbekistan holds significant potential.

Methods. The evolution of the U.S. education market was analyzed based on historical and statistical data. This included examining the number of private and public educational institutions, student enrollment, and the integration of technologies. Specifically, the following data sources were utilized:

Statistics on public and private educational institutions (tables and visuals).

Results of a 2024 parent survey.

Information on EdTech startups and their role in the U.S. market.

Results. Looking at the evolution of the educational services market in the United States, it is evident that the establishment of public schools in the late 18th century and the development of the modern university system marked a turning point in the education sector.[1] Interestingly, the first private university established in the U.S. was Harvard University, founded in 1636 in Cambridge, Massachusetts, by the Massachusetts Bay Colony, almost a century before the establishment of public universities.[2]

In the 1990s, the emergence of online education began with the launch of platforms like “Blackboard” and “WebCT,” [3] which enabled educators to deliver course materials and assessments online. In the early 2000s, EdTech startups such as “Coursera” (2012) [4] and “Khan Academy” (2008) [5] emerged, offering innovative solutions for online and personalized education. In recent years, the private education services market in the U.S. has experienced significant growth, driven by factors such as increased use of technology in education, rising demand for online learning, and a growing interest in lifelong learning.

Traditional entrepreneurial sectors in the U.S. education services market, such as private preschool, elementary and secondary schools, as well as higher education, hold a significant share in this market (Figure 1).

According to the data, as of 2021 [6], the U.S. preschool education system recorded a total of 4.008 million students, the majority of whom (3.58 million) were enrolled in public institutions, while private institutions accounted for 428,000 students. For elementary and secondary schools (2022-23) [7], there were a total of 127,268 schools, with the majority being public schools (97,568) and private schools numbering 29,700. As of 2020-21 [8], there were a total of 5,916 higher education institutions, with private universities (4,024) significantly outnumbering public universities (1,892).

Figure 1. Distribution Between Public and Private Education Sectors in the U.S. [9]

Institution Type	Total Number	Public Institutions	Private Institutions
Preschool Educational Institutions (Student Numbers, 2021)	4,008,000	3,580,000	428,000
Elementary and Secondary Schools (2022-23)	127,268	97,568	29,700
Higher Education Institutions (2020-21)	5,916	1,892	4,024

Analyzing this table in percentage terms (Figure 2), private preschool institutions in 2021 and private schools during the 2022-23 season showed lower coverage and numbers compared to public institutions, at 10.7% and 23.3%, respectively. However, as of 2020-21, private higher education institutions (68%) were almost twice as many as public higher education institutions (32%), indicating that the higher education sector in the U.S. is the most favorable network for education entrepreneurs.

The U.S. boasts a robust market for educational services, with a wide range of private companies offering diverse educational products and services, establishing the country as a global leader in the sector. Companies like “Coursera,” “Udacity,” and “Khan Academy” have gained international recognition for their online education platforms. These platforms often collaborate with universities and educational institutions to offer a wide array of courses. Companies such as “The Princeton Review” and “Kaplan Test Prep” are well-known for their test preparation services for standardized exams like SAT, ACT, and GRE.

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The U.S. is also home to numerous EdTech startups focusing on areas like online learning, personalized education, and educational games. Examples include “Duolingo,” “Quizlet,” and “Codecademy.”

Figure 2. Ratio of Private and Public Educational Institutions in the United States [10]

According to a 2024 survey, 50% of parents who chose private schools in the U.S. for their youngest child cited a safe environment as the primary reason, while 40% indicated education quality as their main consideration. In comparison, 57% of parents who sent their youngest child to public schools mentioned location convenience as the key factor in their decision. [11]

Discussion. Various factors have influenced the development of the private education services sector in the United States, including:

Technology Adoption: The widespread use of technology in the U.S. has facilitated the growth of online education and EdTech startups.

Educational Inequality: Despite significant investments in education, there remain substantial disparities in access to education among students from different socio-economic backgrounds.

High Cost of Education: The high cost of education in the U.S. can be a barrier for many students, particularly those from low-income families.

Regulatory Challenges: The U.S. education system is highly decentralized, with each state having its own rules and standards.

Venture Capital Investments: The U.S. has a well-developed venture capital sector, with many investors ready to fund promising EdTech startups.

Acquisition Opportunities: Many emerging startups in the U.S. opt to merge with larger companies due to intense market competition, high demand, and the cost of meeting regulatory requirements. The EdTech sector in the U.S. has a strong acquisition market, with many major companies actively seeking to acquire promising startups.

The key factors behind the success of the U.S. education market suggest the following recommendations for application in Uzbekistan:

Widespread Adoption of Technology: Investments should be attracted to develop online education platforms in Uzbekistan.

Encouraging the Private Sector: U.S. experience shows that private sector involvement contributes to improving the quality of higher education.

Challenges: Issues such as educational inequality, high costs, and regulatory difficulties require a cautious approach in Uzbekistan.

EdTech Opportunities: Developing partnerships with international EdTech companies is crucial for advancing education in Uzbekistan.

To conclude the U.S. education services market exemplifies a dynamic and innovative ecosystem shaped by its blend of public and private sector efforts. From its historical foundation with public schools and the early establishment of private institutions like Harvard University to the rise of EdTech startups, the evolution of the U.S. education sector highlights the importance of technology, entrepreneurship, and collaboration. Platforms such as "Coursera," "Khan Academy," and "Duolingo" showcase how technology can democratize access to education while addressing diverse learning needs. For Uzbekistan, the U.S. model provides valuable insights. Promoting private sector involvement, adopting advanced technologies, and developing partnerships with international EdTech companies could help modernize the education system. However, these adaptations must consider local challenges, such as equitable access and affordability. By leveraging innovation and fostering public-private collaboration, Uzbekistan can enhance its educational services and meet the demands of a rapidly evolving global market.

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